

Diaspora Engagement and International Relations in the Cold War

Erzsébet Árvay

PhD candidate, Doctoral School of International Relations and Political Science,
Corvinus University of Budapest

Abstract

In the last two decades, a growing number of studies attempted to incorporate diasporas and diasporic activities into the literature of International Relations. The need for incorporation arose seemingly in parallel with the increasing body of literature on diasporas, which stems from the proliferation of diaspora policies. This paper aims to add a historical perspective to the discussion by reviewing the diaspora engagement policies of the Hungarian People's Republic in the context of Soviet bloc states during the Cold War. The study examines the archival sources of Radio Free Europe to explore the state-diaspora relations of Soviet bloc countries in the international system.

The paper applies the inductive method of qualitative textual analysis to examine the documentation of Hungarian diaspora policies and analyse them along with the Czechoslovak, Polish and Romanian policies, as they were recorded by the respective units of Radio Free Europe. The study discusses a novel typology of diaspora engagement policies which is the outcome of the software-assisted qualitative analysis of the archival records. The study reflects on the state-diaspora nexus of the Soviet bloc countries and hence contributes to the literature on diaspora policies of authoritarian states.

Introduction

The study of diaspora engagement policies resulted in the emergence of various new typologies in the last few decades, owing to the numerous comprehensive researches conducted in the field. Previous studies presented comparative analyses between different categories of policies reflecting on the connection between diaspora policies and the political system of states that apply them, and on the role of diasporas in the international system. Even though earlier findings provide excellent insight into the diversity of diaspora policymaking, the literature predominantly discusses liberal democracies, thus, with a few exceptions¹⁴⁹, there is a lack of research on authoritarian states and their diasporas.

My paper speaks to this gap in the literature, and aims at explaining the diaspora policymaking processes of authoritarian states during the Cold War. My paper explores the archival records of Radio Free Europe (RFE) and argues how Radio Free Europe documented, interpreted and reflected on the state-diaspora nexus regarding the Hungarian People's Republic. The main research question is what diaspora engagement policies were recorded by the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe? The paper argues that in order to thoroughly understand the diaspora policies that a state applies, the policies have to be examined in their given political context. In the case of the Hungarian People's Republic, the context is the political system of the Soviet bloc, therefore, the paper analyses the diaspora policies of the Hungarian state along with the Czechoslovak, Polish and Romanian diaspora policies of the era.

My paper also argues that through inductive qualitative research, a typology of diaspora engagement policies can be developed to further analyse the attempts of the state to engage

¹⁴⁹ Notable exceptions include: Gerasimos Tsurapas, "Theorizing State-Diaspora Relations in the Middle East: Authoritarian Emigration States in Comparative Perspective," *Mediterranean Politics* 25, no. 2 (2020): 135–159; Gözde Böcü, "Home and Host Country Policy Interaction in the Making of Turkey's Diasporas," *Middle East Critique* 31, no. 4 (2022): 355-370; Gözde Böcü and Bahar Baser, "Transnational Mobilization of Future Generations by Non-Democratic Home States: Turkey's Diaspora Youth Between Empowerment and Co-optation," *Ethnopolitics* (2022).

with its diasporans. This research applies qualitative textual analysis: the coding of the primary archival sources and the thematic analysis were carried out using NVivo software. The primary sources of the research include the Subject Files and Information Items series of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe that are in the holdings of Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives in Budapest. The archival documents were digitised, and then through the method of thematic analysis, a typology of diaspora engagement policies was created by identifying the core elements of diaspora policymaking of the Hungarian People's Republic.

The empirical research findings discuss the novel typology of diaspora engagement policies that I created on the basis of archival source analysis. The typology differentiates ten major categories of diaspora policies: control policies, cultural policies, institutional building policies, investment policies, mobility policies, political incorporation policies, propaganda policies, redefection policies, social policies and symbolic policies. The categories and subcategories of diaspora policies provide an insight into how employees of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe perceived the state-diaspora relations. The paper explains to what extent the typology that emerged as a result of the qualitative analysis can provide a better understanding of diaspora engagement policies of the Cold War.

Theoretical underpinnings

In order to establish a sound theoretical foundation for the discussion, it is crucial to review the underlying literature in the field of diaspora policies. Since the premise of the present study is the analysis of primary sources, it is worth reviewing how the literature on diaspora studies can contribute to source analysis. As political scientist Francesco Ragazzi argues: "Identifying the characteristic features of diaspora policies is key to assessing the ability of explanatory frameworks to account for these characteristics and their regularities."¹⁵⁰ Ragazzi's argument

¹⁵⁰ Francesco Ragazzi, "A Comparative Analysis of Diaspora Policies," *Political Geography* 41, (July 2014): 76.

gives a short, but thorough rationale for this paper, since this study aims at identifying the aspects of diaspora engagement policies of the Hungarian People's Republic by conducting a thematic analysis of archival documents. The goal of thematic coding is to construct the concepts that define the individual diaspora policies and hence contribute to the development of an explanatory typology.

Considering modern diaspora studies, researchers from the fields of geography, international relations, sociology and ethnology have already developed distinct theoretical frameworks to analyse modern migration processes, diasporic activities, and diaspora policies. However, the historical application of these theoretical frameworks would be anachronistic considering the Cold War period, due to the fact that conceptual frameworks that form the basis of modern diaspora policies and their typologies primarily describe liberal democracies, rather than authoritarian states. Given the above-mentioned critical thought, it should be noted that already existing frameworks can be helpful and highly practical in coding and developing a genuine theoretical framework. Though it may seem contradictory to the previous statement about anachronism, the review of modern typologies can be helpful since it reflects the process of analysing diaspora policies and creating explanatory frameworks.

In his 2014 article, Ragazzi differentiates three distinct but interconnected frameworks of diaspora policies: the structural-instrumental framework, the ethnic conception hypothesis and the governmentality framework. The structural-instrumental framework argues that states behave in accordance with their position at either the core or the periphery of the world economy.¹⁵¹ The ethnic conception hypothesis claims that a diaspora policy of a state is a response to the challenges of globalisation.¹⁵² Ragazzi argues that, though the structural-

¹⁵¹ Ragazzi, "A Comparative Analysis," 82.

¹⁵² Ragazzi, "A Comparative Analysis," 82.

instrumental framework and the ethnic conception hypothesis give an insight into the factors that determine diaspora policies, taking only material factors or ethnic conceptions of citizenship into consideration cannot lead to a thorough framework for analysing diaspora policies.¹⁵³ He therefore suggests the governmentality framework. According to his definition of the concept: “diaspora policies are shaped by modifications in programs of government and practices of power,” later adding “governmentality assumes a strong link between the types of political-economic rationalities and regimes (planned economy, welfare state, neo-liberal state) and diaspora policies.”¹⁵⁴ As Ragazzi argues, the governmentality framework gives a broader political-economic context for analysing state interests and diaspora policies.¹⁵⁵

Considering governmentality, geographer and migration scholar Alan Gamlen goes further than Ragazzi by presenting a typology of diaspora engagement policies within the governmentality framework. Gamlen argues that there are three types of diaspora engagement policies: capacity building policies, extending rights to the diaspora, and extracting obligations from the diaspora.¹⁵⁶ Within these higher-level policies, Gamlen differentiates subareas of diaspora policies. Within capacity building policies, Gamlen distinguishes symbolic nation-building and institutional building policies; policies of extending rights include practices aiming at political incorporation and providing civil and social services to emigrants; finally, by extracting obligation Gamlen means investment policies and lobby promotions.¹⁵⁷

Peggy Levitt and Rafael de la Dehesa point out that diaspora policies reconfigure “the traditional understanding of sovereignty, nation and citizenship,”¹⁵⁸ while Gamlen argues that

¹⁵³ Ragazzi, “A Comparative Analysis,” 82-87.

¹⁵⁴ Ragazzi, “A Comparative Analysis,” 82.

¹⁵⁵ Ragazzi, “A Comparative Analysis,” 87.

¹⁵⁶ Alan J. Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement Policies: What are they and what kinds of states use them?,” *Working Paper* 32 (Oxford: University of Oxford, 2006), 5-6.

¹⁵⁷ Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement,” 6-18.

¹⁵⁸ Peggy Levitt and Rafael de la Dehesa, “Transnational Migration and the Redefinition of the State: Variations and Explanations,” *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 26, no. 4 (2003): 606.

“diaspora engagement policies (re)produce citizen-sovereign relationships with expatriates, thus transnationalizing governmentality.”¹⁵⁹ Thus, we can see that conducting diaspora policies means (re)gaining legitimate power over expatriates. Gamlen also highlights that such policies “cannot be seen as singular, discrete, or historically *sui generis*. Rather, they form a constellation of institutional and legislative arrangements and programmes that come into being at different times, for different reasons, and operate across different timescales at different levels within the state.”¹⁶⁰ Therefore, taking a wider time frame, such as the Cold War, provides space for problematising the dimension of time within the typology of diaspora engagement policies, since it can allow for deeper analysis, and in this way, it is possible to explore not only which policies were created, but also the whys and hows of diaspora policymaking. A wider time frame can also help understand the transformation of the institutional system of diaspora policies.

As political theorist Szabolcs Pogonyi argues, one of the variables of diaspora policies that one should consider is agency.¹⁶¹ Pogonyi quotes Stéphane Dufoix saying that considering diaspora as the initiator of engagement policies reflects on the various conflicting interests of heterogeneous diasporas.¹⁶² Anthropologist Michel S. Laguerre also points out in his 1998 publication that “the diaspora can be seen as a political agency.”¹⁶³ This political agency acts in a transnational political field, which is, according to Laguerre, “an open arena in which elected and non-elected individuals, with or without the explicit knowledge of the state – and sometimes acting against official state policies – engage formal and informal political practices

¹⁵⁹ Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement,” 4-5.

¹⁶⁰ Gamlen, “Diaspora Engagement,” 20.

¹⁶¹ Pogonyi Szabolcs, “Transborder Kin-minority as Symbolic Resource in Hungary,” *Journal on Ethnopolitics and Minority Issues in Europe* 14, no. 3 (2015): 76.

¹⁶² Pogonyi, “Transborder Kin-minority,” 78.

¹⁶³ Michel S. Laguerre, *Diasporic Citizenship: Haitian Americans in Transnational America* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 1998), 157.

for the purpose of influencing the everyday policies and politics of another state.”¹⁶⁴ Considering the Cold War context, such a transnational political agency meant a threat to the Soviet bloc countries since it challenged the authority of the state. This thought is reflected in Sławomir Łukasiewicz’s work, who argues that emigration from a Soviet bloc country was considered as “an act of contestation against the political system,”¹⁶⁵ in other words a “mechanism for delegitimizing” the political authority of the sending state.¹⁶⁶

Yossi Shain argues that diasporas are capable of independent political actions;¹⁶⁷ moreover they can serve as “bearers for the ideals of recovery and restoration.”¹⁶⁸ From the perspective of a dictatorial regime, diasporas’ capacity for restoration can be understood as a delegitimising process against the leadership of the regime. Shain adds four concerns of diasporas that influence diasporic activities regarding conflict resolution: maintaining their ethnic identity, competition for leadership of the transnational community, organisational interest, and other political interests of diasporas.¹⁶⁹ These activities and interests are important from the point of view of the present study since diaspora policies do not necessarily appear explicitly in the primary sources, but as reactions to certain diasporic activities.

The theoretical background of this study is visibly interdisciplinary; however, there are core elements that greatly help the coding process of the primary sources. Firstly, Ragazzi’s argumentation draws attention to segments of the archival documents that reflect on the practices of the Hungarian state as a sovereign power, through which the state tried to extend its authority over the emigrant communities. Secondly, Gamlen’s typology and Levitt and

¹⁶⁴ Laguerre, *Diasporic Citizenship*, 158.

¹⁶⁵ Sławomir Łukasiewicz, “The Polish Political System in Exile, 1945-1990,” *Polish American Studies* 72, no. 2 (Autumn 2015): 29.

¹⁶⁶ Łukasiewicz, “The Polish Political System,” 29.

¹⁶⁷ Yossi Shain, “The Role of Diasporas in Conflict Perpetuation or Resolution,” *SAIS Review* 12, no. 2 (2002): 116.

¹⁶⁸ Shain, “The Role of Diasporas,” 118.

¹⁶⁹ Shain, “The Role of Diasporas,” 128.

Dehesa's notion of sovereignty raises questions, such as: what institutional system served the policymaking process of the Hungarian state, what rights of émigrés were recognised by the state, and how the Hungarian state tried to exploit its émigrés. Lastly, Laguerre's, Łukasiewicz's, and Shain's works focus the coding process on diasporic activities that could evoke a response from the Hungarian state in the form of diaspora policies. This paper addresses issues which could contribute to the understanding of the relations between the Soviet bloc countries and their diasporic communities by further exploring the unique dynamics of the diaspora engagement policies of the era, which could help us to reveal the structural changes in the state-diaspora connections in the Soviet bloc.

Methodology and the Primary Sources

The method applied in the present research is a thematic analysis based on qualitative text coding. Qualitative text coding is a process which aims at analysing and organising textual data in order to find significant, generalizable patterns. Qualitative text coding divides the textual data into codes, categories or labels that are characteristic of a specific theme or phenomenon. Coding can help researchers to "establish a framework of thematic ideas" about the text.¹⁷⁰ I carried out the data-driven coding in NVivo, and then I condensed the emerging codes, categories, and themes into a typology of diaspora engagement policies, which, therefore, reflects the hierarchy of the coding tree.

As mentioned in the previous section, the theoretical literature on diaspora policies greatly helped the coding process by suggesting subquestions of the research. Apart from the main research question on the diaspora engagement policies of the Hungarian People's Republic, the research focused on the following subquestions: 1.) Through what practices did the Hungarian state try to engage with its émigrés? 2.) What institutional system served the diaspora

¹⁷⁰ Graham R. Gibbs, *Analyzing Qualitative Data* (London: Sage Publications Ltd, 2007), 38.

policymaking process of the Hungarian state? 3.) What rights of émigrés were recognised/denied by the state? 4.) What diasporic activities could evoke a response from the Hungarian state? These subquestions helped the research by constantly refocusing the coding process on data segments that are relevant to the study.

The primary sources of the research are archival records of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe. In order to contextualize the archival documents, it is worth discussing a few pieces of background information on the source material. Radio Free Europe (RFE) was established in 1949, with the aim of directing Western propaganda towards the Soviet satellite states.¹⁷¹ RFE broadcast uncensored radio programmes behind the Iron Curtain with the purpose of competing with the heavily censored local radio stations of Czechoslovakia, Hungary, Poland, Bulgaria, Albania, and Romania. Though Radio Free Europe tried to cover its ties to any Western governments, the radio was an instrument of US foreign policy.¹⁷²

In order to achieve Western propaganda goals, it was important that radio programmes broadcast reliable information. Therefore, RFE paid special attention to the collection and analysis of sources through the News and Information Service division. The division provided press monitoring transcripts, reports from Field Offices that were located all over Europe, background analyses, and research studies for the different broadcasting Units of RFE.¹⁷³ The most important documents from the archival records of RFE for the present research are the information items, which contain reports based on interviews conducted with the escapees in Western European countries. Today, these reports serve as primary sources on the political and economic systems of Soviet bloc countries, including reports on the policies through which the Hungarian state tried to engage with its émigré communities.

¹⁷¹ Robert Holt, *Radio Free Europe* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1958), 3.

¹⁷² Holt, *Radio Free Europe*, 3-4.

¹⁷³ Holt, *Radio Free Europe*, 98-109.

The coding and analysis of the relevant reports reveal what diaspora policies of the Hungarian state Radio Free Europe documented during the Cold War. It is crucial to note though that the primary sources reflect the viewpoint of RFE, therefore, the present study provides a meso-level analysis of diaspora engagement. Thus, the typology of diaspora policies, which is presented in the following section, sheds light on how Radio Free Europe perceived state-diaspora relations.

Documentation of Hungarian Diaspora Policies by Radio Free Europe

My analysis of the reports of the Hungarian Unit of Radio Free Europe led to the creation of ten categories of diaspora engagement policies, as it is summarised in *Table 1*: control policies, cultural policies, institutional building policies, investment policies, mobility policies, political incorporation policies, propaganda policies, redefection policies, social policies and symbolic policies.

Control policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Controlling contact with émigrés ▪ Monitoring policies ▪ Harassment practices
Cultural policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing cultural institutions ▪ Organising conferences ▪ Organising summer universities ▪ Organising other cultural activities
Institutional building policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing consulate services ▪ Establishing ministerial-level agencies ▪ Maintaining World Federation of Hungarians
Investment policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic policies ▪ Knowledge remittance policies
Mobility policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Issuing passports ▪ Issuing visas ▪ Denying re-entry to home state ▪ Restricting exit and transit policies
Political incorporation policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Citizenship policies ▪ Sanctioning policies ▪ Granting amnesty
Propaganda policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Broadcasting “Homeland” radio program ▪ Press ▪ Communicating with émigrés
Redefection policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Extending appeals towards émigrés ▪ Contacting émigrés

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Establishing institutional background for the redefection campaign
Social policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organising social activities ▪ Providing free-of-charge dispensary ▪ Establishing pensioner homes for elderly returnees
Symbolic policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organising diaspora conferences ▪ Organising meetings with high-ranked state representatives

Table 1

The first type of policies to discuss is control policies. This category emerged from the segments that described situations or reported on events in which Hungarian authorities tried to level a certain degree of state control over either citizens who had connections with émigrés, or over visiting and returning émigrés. Control policies consist of three subcategories, as *Table 1* shows, namely controlling contact with émigrés, monitoring practices, and harassment practices.

Controlling any kind of contact with émigrés abroad manifested in actions such as forcing citizens to write letters to their émigré relatives to inform them about policies introduced in their home state,¹⁷⁴ or to inform them that Hungarian authorities were aware of their political activities.¹⁷⁵ Authorities also tried to force citizens who visited Western countries to contact émigrés and obtain information from them.¹⁷⁶ Controlling contact with émigrés also meant, in some cases, the restriction of communication in order to stop the flow of information in both directions.¹⁷⁷

Monitoring practices describe both the surveillance of communication with émigrés¹⁷⁸ and of relatives of émigrés residing in Hungary.¹⁷⁹ Harassment practices were carried out within the

¹⁷⁴ “Restrictions on passports issuance” 12 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁵ “Atmosphere of distrust and suspicion growing against relatives of defectors” 19 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁶ “Hungarian authorities’ interest in refugees’ reaction to consular passport” 27 September 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁷⁷ “The regime’s attitude towards Hungarians living abroad” 19 January 1968. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁸ “Persons having contact with refugees being checked” 23 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁷⁹ “Censorship – foreign currency offenses” 19 December 1967. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/3.

border of the state, however, they affected émigrés who visited the countries. Reports reveal cases according to which visiting émigrés were harassed by Hungarian authorities, in some cases their visas were confiscated,¹⁸⁰ and in several other cases visiting émigrés were threatened up to the point when they finally “voluntarily” gave up their intention to leave the country again.¹⁸¹

The second type of diaspora engagement policies is cultural policies. Within this category, as *Table 1* presents, there are four subcategories, namely establishing cultural institutions, organising conferences, summer universities, and other cultural activities. While summer universities predominantly aimed at promoting Hungarian language learning, scientific conferences dealt with a wide range of topics, hence, the two subcategories are labelled separately. Other cultural activities include cultural evenings and commemoration of historical events organised by the Hungarian legation. As can be seen, policies concerning cultural activities were much less varied than the above-mentioned control policies.

Reports on the establishment of cultural institutions predominantly deal with the Hungarian Houses that were established in several Western countries. These cultural institutions were state founded and often used to provide a platform for the dissemination of state propaganda.¹⁸² Apart from state-funded institutions, much emphasis was put on engaging with the diaspora through cultural ties, such as language learning. Since 1970, the World Association of Hungarians had organised conferences in order to discuss the status of the Hungarian Language in the diaspora and to arrange training for teachers of the Hungarian language.¹⁸³ The Mother Tongue conference soon became one of the most successful projects of the state-controlled World Association of Hungarians. Language learning opportunities were offered through summer

¹⁸⁰ “Emigrant visiting Hungary prevented from returning to US” 23 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/10.

¹⁸¹ “Former Hungarian citizen visitors detained in Hungary” 26 October 1963. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁸² “Current activity of the regime-sponsored Hungarian House in Paris” 29 March 1962. HU OSA 300-40-4:2/18.

¹⁸³ “Hungarians abroad should learn Hungarian” 14 August 1970. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/4.

universities and summer camps,¹⁸⁴ which also provided an opportunity to build up the reputation of Hungary among diasporans.

The third category of diaspora policies is institutional building policies. In this category, institutions do not cover cultural institutions, but consulate services and ministerial-level agencies. *Table 1* shows the different layers of this policy. As the coding process revealed, consulate services served the purpose of providing information for émigrés, especially about redefection possibilities,¹⁸⁵ and also providing diplomatic and passport services, besides monitoring émigrés and their connection with the home state and the recipient country.¹⁸⁶ Two key institutions were repeatedly discussed in the reports, the Independent Agency of Hungarians Abroad and the World Federation of Hungarians (sometimes mentioned as World Associations of Hungarians), which served the purpose of engaging with diasporas and influencing their organisations.¹⁸⁷

During the coding process, as *Table 1* shows, two major types of investment policies were detected: economic policies and knowledge remittance policies. The concept of knowledge remittance reflects on the activities of the state through which diasporans were encouraged to engage in scientific networks with their homeland, such as networking opportunities provided by scientific conferences.¹⁸⁸ Interestingly, all the reports discussing scientific connections, originate in the late 1980s, or at least no earlier attempts were recorded by RFE.

Economic policies predominantly relied on émigrés' foreign contacts and their financial capacity and they aimed at increasing the inflow of hard currency to Hungary.¹⁸⁹ Confiscating

¹⁸⁴ "Courses for young Hungarians living abroad" 17 July 1975. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/4.

¹⁸⁵ "Announcement by the Hungarian legation in London on the amnesty" 11 July 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/22.

¹⁸⁶ "Recent Aspects of Redefection Campaign" 16 January 1956. HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

¹⁸⁷ "Hungarian government's link with Hungarians abroad" 13 August 1986. HU OSA 300-40-2:22/3.

¹⁸⁸ "East European Governments' Attitude," HU OSA 300-40-1:257/2.

¹⁸⁹ "Situation concerning foreign currency" 22 November 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:19/3.

émigrés' properties that were left behind when they left the country was another attempt to increase income, especially in the case of confiscated flats that were later re-sold.¹⁹⁰

The fifth category of diaspora engagement policies is mobility policies. Policies included in this category are in connection with the issuance of passports and visas, or restriction on the movement of citizens. As *Table 1* presents, records of Radio Free Europe focused on four types of travel documents: consular passports,¹⁹¹ re-entry visas, visitor visas and exit visas.¹⁹² Since the process of issuing travel documents and refusal of issuance were discussed in separate reports of RFE, different subcategories were developed to represent them.

Refusal of the issuance of travel documents was justified by authorities on the pretext of political activities against the Hungarian state or of the actions of emigrant relatives.¹⁹³ Denial of re-entry was justified by a quite loose description of activities: “persons who have given away state secrets, defamed the Hungarian social order, have contacted hostile organisations or have caused any other harm to the country, will be refused permissions for returning home.”¹⁹⁴ Considering the fact that émigré organisations which were not under the control of the Hungarian state were believed to be hostile, the above-mentioned justification could be used whenever it was in the interest of the authorities.

Table 1 also introduces the category of political incorporation policies. Political incorporation is understood as a set of policies aimed at engaging and integrating émigrés into the political system of the Hungarian state. Citizenship policies include both extending political rights by

¹⁹⁰ “Refugee property in Hungary” 10 April 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁹¹ “Circular from Vienna Hungarian legation to Hungarian emigrants concerning citizenship” 5 December 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹² “Disappointment with émigré Hungarians” 11 September 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/10.

¹⁹³ “Wording of Refusal to persons applying for visit to relatives in the West” 13 September 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹⁴ “Népszabadság says defectors may return” 9 June 1975. HU OSA 300-40-2:23/1.

naturalisation, re-naturalisation or allowing dual citizenship,¹⁹⁵ and restricting political rights by loss of citizenship or renunciation of citizenship.¹⁹⁶

Another form of political incorporation is granting amnesty in an attempt to encourage émigrés to return to Hungary.¹⁹⁷ Sanctioning policies, for example, criminalising emigration,¹⁹⁸ might be seen as contradictory to incorporation; however, it is important to highlight that inverse incorporation also assumes that the state extends its control over the citizen. As in the case of all political incorporation policies, the interest of the state, instead of the interest of émigrés, provides the perspective for analysis. Therefore, even though incorporation might implicate beneficial policies, because of the interest of a closed regime, sanctioning policies are also included in this category.

The category of propaganda policies has three subcategories, two of them depicting the means of channelling propaganda, namely broadcasting “Homeland” radio programmes and press. The Homeland radio programme tried to engage with diasporans on several levels, it broadcast accounts of redefectors, letters of refugees and messages to emigrant relatives¹⁹⁹ in order to present an ideally depicted connection between émigrés and their relatives living in the home country. The radio programme also focused on the cultural developments and economic progress of the home state,²⁰⁰ as well as providing youth and sports programmes for the wider audience.²⁰¹

¹⁹⁵ “Hungarian House in Paris Advertises Consular Passports” 14 July 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹⁶ “Former Hungarian citizen visitors detained in Hungary,” HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14. And: “Means of obtaining release from Hungarian Citizenship” 15 March 1963. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

¹⁹⁷ “Kádár announces amnesty” 22 March 1963. HU OSA 300-40-1:17/4.

¹⁹⁸ “Refugee sentenced in absentia” 23 January 1967. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.; “Campaign against refugees” 23 December 1965. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

¹⁹⁹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰¹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

As part of propaganda campaigns, the press had an effect predominantly on a domestic level, the majority of the archival records deals with how the press tried to formulate public opinion within state borders. Firstly, the press tried depicting émigré life as empty and dire, so citizens would give up their plans for leaving the country.²⁰² Another practice was to publish accounts by redefectors on the hardships of exile life or the letters of homesick exiles.²⁰³ The redefection campaign was also propagated by the press through the publishing of news on the campaign itself and representing the reunited families.²⁰⁴

A subcategory of propaganda policies is communication with émigrés. During the coding process, two types of communication were revealed within this category, encouraged communication and exploitive communication. It is important to highlight at this point that there is a crucial distinction between forced communication, which is discussed under control policies, and encouraged communication. The reason why these two types of communication are presented separately is the fact that according to the reports, encouraged communication served propaganda purposes,²⁰⁵ while forced communication, as was discussed earlier, served the purpose of controlling communication with émigrés.²⁰⁶ Exploitive communication also served the state propaganda by using émigrés to disseminate favourable information about Hungary abroad.²⁰⁷

The most immensely detailed diaspora engagement policy in the reports of RFE was the redefection policies. Generally, the redefection campaign of the state aimed at persuading émigrés to permanently return to Hungary, and perhaps this is the exact reason why Radio Free

²⁰² “The Situation of the Press – RFE” 7 December 1965. HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

²⁰³ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁵ “The regime’s attitude towards Hungarians living abroad,” HU OSA 300-40-4:21/1.

²⁰⁶ “Hungarian authorities’ interest in refugees’ reaction to consular passport” 27 September 1961. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/14.

²⁰⁷ “Emigráció, 1961-1986” 1963. HU OSA 300-40-3:9/64.

Europe made such an effort to report on that issue. *Table 1* lists the various elements of the redefection policies.

Extending appeals towards émigrés intended to emotionally manipulate émigrés to persuade them about returning. Within this category, the coding process revealed the subcategory of communicating the dissatisfaction of exile life by stressing the shameful and insulting conditions of émigrés' life and the hostile environment that surrounded them.²⁰⁸ The second subcategory is communicating about the economic interest of exiles through means of channelling state propaganda on the industrial progress of Hungary or the opportunities for employment.²⁰⁹ Awakening the sense of national identification and awakening the sense of family are describing actions through which the state aimed at creating the image of a welcoming homeland and family.²¹⁰

Redefection policies also include the subcategories of contacting émigrés and establishing institutions. Both of them emerged from the coding of reports that discussed forms of communication or establishment of institutions which concerned the redefection campaign of the state. In order to channel the campaign abroad, state representatives tried to personally approach émigrés²¹¹ or wrote official letters to get in touch with diasporans.²¹² To create the institutional background for the redefection campaign, the state set up repatriation committees and local information offices that provided assistance for redefectors.²¹³

The last two types of diaspora policies were social policies and symbolic policies. Social policies provided either social events for émigrés or aid for the ones in need. The subcategory

²⁰⁸ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²⁰⁹ "Special Document issued to repatriates in Paris" 3 October 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/23.

²¹⁰ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²¹¹ "Visit of Hungarian legation officials to Hungarians now living and working in Wolverhampton" 17 August 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/22.

²¹² "Global analysis of the repatriation action" 6 October 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/23.

²¹³ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

of organising social activities refers to the reports which discussed social evenings organised by the Hungarian legation in foreign countries in order to attract diasporans and establish contact with them.²¹⁴ There is one report from 1959 which revealed that the Hungarian legation provided a free-of-charge dispensary²¹⁵ for diasporans in Paris, and another interesting report from 1985, which claims that the Hungarian state established pensioner homes for elderly returnees.²¹⁶ Even though these single reports do not discuss the social benefits in detail, they were included in the coding process as particular elements of diaspora engagement policies.

Symbolic policies are rarely mentioned in the reports of RFE, only a few instances reflect on the fact that even a dictatorial regime realised the importance of symbolic actions towards émigrés. Organising diaspora conferences first appears in the archival sources in 1983.²¹⁷ Diaspora conferences are aimed at providing a platform for engaging with members of the diasporic community and discussing issues regarding émigré life. Records on organising meetings with high-ranked state representatives date back to 1988, one of the most debated events was the meeting between Károly Grósz and émigrés in New York.²¹⁸

As we can see, the coding process resulted in the emergence of categories and subcategories of various types of diaspora engagement policies. Although the discussed codes introduce exciting topics to further analyse, it should be emphasised that only the perspective of Radio Free Europe is reflected in the reports on the diaspora engagement policies. Therefore, only meso-level analysis can be based on the typology presented above.

²¹⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.

²¹⁵ “The repatriation of Hungarian refugees from France survey of January 1959” 6 March 1959. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/18.

²¹⁶ “Emigráció, 1961-1986” 1985. HU OSA 300-40-3:9/64.

²¹⁷ “Association of Hungarians Meets in Budapest” 5 December 1983. HU OSA 300-40-1:1112/1.

²¹⁸ “Grosz and the Hungarian emigre community in the USA” 3 August 1988. HU OSA 300-40-2:22/3.

Contextualising Diaspora Policies

After a closer look at the established typology of the Hungarian diaspora policies, there are a number of parallels that can be drawn between the diaspora policies of the satellite states. Radio Free Europe, as a covert organisation of the CIA, aimed at channelling propaganda to the Soviet bloc countries.²¹⁹ The different units of Radio Free Europe created background reports on the so-called Soviet satellite states and their diasporas in order to provide a broad perspective for the anti-Communist propaganda. As Michael Cude and Ellen Paul point out regarding Czech and Slovak émigrés' role at RFE, their contribution meant that the anti-Communist perspective of the exile community could reach Czechoslovakia through the broadcasts.²²⁰ Reports on the Czechoslovak, Polish, and Romanian diaspora policies predominantly dealt with the redefection campaign of the satellite states. As a report from January 1956 details,²²¹ one of the most influential efforts of the Soviet bloc regimes was the redefection campaign which aimed at refugees living in camps in Germany and Austria, but also at the broader rank and file of the exile community in Western countries. The methods that were applied by the Soviet bloc countries show some similarities with the Hungarian redefection campaign.

The redefection campaign of the Czechoslovak state applied various methods to persuade refugees and émigrés to return to their home country. One of these methods was a letter campaign in which redefectors were forced to write letters to exiles about the appeals of returning to the home country, describing all the benefits that were offered by the state to the returnees.²²² Extorted letters were a method often used by campaigns of other satellite states as well, given the personal tone of those letters and the potential emotional manipulation that the letters could mean in the hands of the state authorities. Similar methods were observed in the

²¹⁹ Holt, *Radio Free Europe*, 3.

²²⁰ Michael Cude and Ellen Paul, "Czechoslovakia," in *East Central European Migrations During the Cold War*, ed. Anna Mazurkiewicz (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2019), 122.

²²¹ "Recent Aspects of the Redefection Campaign" 16 January 1956. HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 16-25.

²²² "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 17-18.

Polish Unit of Radio Free Europe. The methods used by the Polish state show a rich variety of practices: letter-writing, personal approaches, and organisational work to reach exiled communities or individuals.²²³ The same practice can be observed in the case of the Hungarian state as well, which tried to exploit returnees to channel redefection propaganda home and abroad.²²⁴

Redefectors were used for propaganda purposes not only in the letter-writing campaign. As one of the reports of the Hungarian Unit of RFE puts it: “As a rule, all returnees are exploited for the same propaganda purposes: they depict life in the West with the gloomiest colours and have bitter words against the Western broadcasting stations, among them also against RFE for having moved them to escape the country by lies.”²²⁵ Another report alleges that forced interviews were made with returnees during which scripted answers were given to the authorities.²²⁶

Soviet satellite states commonly established an institutional background for their respective redefection campaigns. In the case of Czechoslovakia, the institutional background for the campaign was provided by the “Committee to Care for Amnestied Refugees Returning to Czechoslovakia”, interestingly – as the report highlights – no notable or prominent Communist political figure contributed openly to the committee or the campaign.²²⁷ The official state representation in the redefection campaign were the embassies that contacted local exiles to inform them about the amnesty decrees and the possibility to return to the home state.²²⁸ This distinct separation of state institutions from repatriation committees and the concealing of state involvement in the work of committees are recurring elements of the reports. In the case of Romania, the institutional background for the redefection campaign was also carefully designed

²²³ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 28.

²²⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 7-9.

²²⁵ “Re-emigrants” 21 September 1955. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/19.

²²⁶ “Interrogation of redefectors” 10 April 1957. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/18.”

²²⁷ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 19.

²²⁸ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 21.

by setting up the “Committee for Repatriation” which had authority over the publication of newspapers and the operation of a radio station in order to facilitate the return of émigrés.²²⁹

Contrary to the Czechoslovak case, the repatriation committee in Romania included well-known Communist political figures.²³⁰

Meanwhile, sources on the Hungarian redefection campaign use different names for the institutional background. One report from 1956 refers to a “repatriation committee”²³¹ that served the interest of the Hungarian campaign, and another source from 1958 makes a reference to a “Committee to Promote the Return Home of Hungarians.”²³² A report of the Hungarian Unit from 1957 refers to “the repatriation commissions which are working under the supervision of the Legation”²³³ and later adds: “In other countries, the whole redefection procedure is handled by the Legations.”²³⁴ Not only the Hungarian Legation involved itself in the redefection campaign; but reports on the Czechoslovak campaign also claimed that local embassies were in contact with exile diasporans to channel the news about the opportunity of returning to their home state.²³⁵

Channelling the propaganda about the redefection campaign was done through various means. In the Czechoslovakian campaign, the publication of *Hlas Domova* (Voice of Homeland) magazine served this purpose, because it was circulated among exile communities.²³⁶ The magazine provided information about redefectors experiences after returning to Czechoslovakia, and also about amnesty decrees issued by the home state. The Czechoslovakian state – in some way or another – tried to channel the following appeals

²²⁹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 39.

²³⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 39-40.

²³¹ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 8.

²³² “The East Berlin Repatriation Committee” 12 February 1958. HU OSA 300-40-4:20/17.

²³³ “Redefection propaganda and procedure” 6 April 1957. HU OSA 300-40-1:258/2.

²³⁴ “Redefection propaganda and procedure,” HU OSA 300-40-1:258/2.

²³⁵ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 21.

²³⁶ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 17-19.

towards émigrés: economic prosperity in the home state, personal free life at home, dissatisfactions of exile life, a sense of family, and a sense of national identification.²³⁷ The reports show a simple formula: the state depicted an ideal and free life with economic benefits for returnees, while also degrading the exiled way of life and evoking a sense of guilt in émigrés for leaving their home country and relatives behind.

The Polish state introduced a radio broadcast entitled *Kraj* (Homeland) to reach out to the diaspora.²³⁸ The well-orchestrated communication channels served the propaganda machinery of the Polish state in order to provide information on the home country that could counterbalance the anti-Communist propaganda from politically active exile communities. The target of the propaganda campaign was, at first, the professionals and intellectuals of the émigré community. Later, the focus of the campaign broadened and included refugees in general.²³⁹ Thus, we can see that considerable attention was directed to creating and gradually building up the state propaganda in order to successfully reach émigrés and convince them to return to their home states.

Contrary to the appeals of the Czechoslovak redefection propaganda, the Polish campaign had two basic appeals: a sense of national identification and dissatisfaction with exile life; however, it put more emphasis on discrediting the leaders of politically active members of the emigration.²⁴⁰ The importance of the sense of national identification was a recurring theme of Polish state propaganda, which tried to establish a monopoly over Polish culture, language, and history.²⁴¹ Interestingly, while the redefection campaign in both the Czechoslovak and the Polish cases made considerable efforts to communicate the appeals of returning home, neither

²³⁷ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 24-25.

²³⁸ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 28.

²³⁹ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 26-27.

²⁴⁰ "Recent Aspects," HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 37-38.

²⁴¹ "East European Governments' Attitude," HU OSA 300-40-1:257/2, 33.

visa nor passport policies were propagated openly to provide possible returnees with information on the means of re-entering the home state.

The Romanian Committee for Repatriation published a newspaper entitled *Glasul Patriei* (Voice of Homeland), and it propagated similar appeals to the previously mentioned Czechoslovak and Polish campaigns, namely the hardships of exile life, the economic progress in the homeland and employment opportunities.²⁴² Comparing these reports to the Hungarian campaign presents a vast variety of the already-mentioned appeals. The first appeal is awakening “the sense of family” by picturing “the loneliness of the loved ones at home”, “the need for help at home”, “the forgiveness for having deserted the home” and the “loving arms of the family”.²⁴³ The second major appeal is the “economic self-interest” of exiles evoked by channelling “opportunities for employment at home” and presenting the “industrial expansion and progress at home”.²⁴⁴ The third appeal is “national identification” provoked by creating the picture of the “welcoming home”, the “forgiveness for having sinned against the Fatherland”, the “nobility of the Fatherland”, the “history and folklore of Hungary” and the “symbols of the Fatherland.”²⁴⁵ The last appeal is presenting the “dissatisfactions of exile life” by depicting the “lonesomeness, solitude, rootlessness of exile” life, the “hostile environment surrounding the exile”, the “shameful and insulting conditions of exile life” and émigrés’ “treatment as a foreigner.”²⁴⁶

The Hungarian campaign utilised both the radio and the press as well. The Homeland radio programme targeted Hungarian émigrés living in Western European countries, but residents of Hungary were also considered as the target audience. As the report suggests, the fact “that the

²⁴² “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 40.

²⁴³ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

²⁴⁴ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

²⁴⁵ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

²⁴⁶ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 15.

programs were also designed to implement the domestic aspects of the redefection campaign is suggested by the fact that they are transmitted on both the short and medium (Kossuth) wavebands.”²⁴⁷ The Hungarian state also published a periodical entitled *Magyar Hírek* (Hungarian News), and some reports reflect on the distribution of the paper: “The World Federation of Hungarians publishes a periodical called *Magyar Hírek* (Hungarian News) which appears twice a month and of which 85,000 free copies are sent abroad. It also produces a calendar every December.”²⁴⁸

Apart from the many similarities, the reports of the national Units of RFE contain some peculiarities, such as a report on the attempts of the Romanian state to penetrate the émigré community by sending abroad priests of the Bucharest Orthodox Patriarchy.²⁴⁹ The cooperation of the state and church concerning diaspora engagement policies was seemingly not observed or analysed in the Czechoslovak or Polish cases. A reappearing endeavour in the reports is the issuance of amnesty decrees. The reports of the Romanian Unit highlight the impact of the amnesty decree of 1955, which pardoned all crimes (except for murder) committed by Romanian citizens living in exile at that time, in case they decided to return to Romania.²⁵⁰

The means and methods of engaging with the diasporas of the satellite states were apparently rather similar. However, it has to be emphasised that since the origin of these reports in all cases is Radio Free Europe, this common origin surely had its impact on the creation, and hence, the similarities of the reports. By contextualising the primary sources of the research and carrying out a systematic analysis of the developed typology and the existing literature on the topic, my

²⁴⁷ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 6-7.

²⁴⁸ “World Federation of Hungarians Situation Report” 27 April 1976. HU OSA 300-40-1:1112/5.

²⁴⁹ “East European Governments’ Attitude,” HU OSA 300-40-1:257/2, 38.

²⁵⁰ “Recent Aspects,” HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8, 39.

paper attempted to draw results that could be relevant to the framework of diaspora engagement policies of the Cold War era.

Conclusion

Modern diaspora studies put considerable emphasis on creating explanatory frameworks and typologies for a better understanding of diaspora policies. However, the typologies discussed earlier have not treated the context of the examined policies in much detail. This led us to the realisation that in spite of the numerous studies about diaspora policy-making, there is a research gap to be further explored. The significance of the present study lies in the fact that it is based on the qualitative method of thematic analysis. Although qualitative research is suitable only for the analysis of smaller amounts of data, it can explore deeper correlations owing to its capability to construct concepts and typologies, instead of only providing descriptive analysis.

This study, therefore, explored diaspora engagement policies of the Cold War era by analysing reports of the different units of Radio Free Europe as primary sources of the research. The aim of the research was to investigate how diaspora engagement policies are reflected in the sources and to reveal the interconnections between diaspora policies of Soviet bloc countries. The key results of this analysis were summarized in the typology of diaspora policies.

The typology of diaspora engagement policies that I developed as a result of the archival research differentiates ten major categories of diaspora policies: control policies, cultural policies, institutional building policies, investment policies, mobility policies, political incorporation policies, propaganda policies, redefection policies, social policies and symbolic policies. The categories, subcategories, and codes of diaspora policies provided an insight into how Radio Free Europe perceived state-diaspora relations. Moreover, they helped to detect what further primary sources should be analysed, due to the fact that the emerging categories shed light on the mechanisms of diaspora policy-making. Therefore, future research should be

carried out that includes more diverse types of primary sources, which could help to reach theoretical saturation.

The study revealed that exploring the Cold War diaspora policy-making in the context of the Soviet bloc states provides deep analytical opportunities. As the Czechoslovak, Polish and Romanian cases proved, there are numerous parallels to be drawn between the diaspora policies of the satellite states. The sources shed light on the common historical context that could also serve as a basis for future research, since the comparative analysis of the diaspora policies of the Soviet satellite states is hitherto an untapped research field. The paper also showed that, although several researches explored the state-diaspora nexus so far, no comprehensive research has been carried out yet which could integrate the various aspects of state-diaspora relations.

Bibliography

Archival sources

HU OSA 300-5-40:13/8.; Records of Aurél Bereznai: Subject Files; Analytic Research Department; Records of Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty Research Institute; Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives at Central European University, Budapest.

HU OSA 300-40-1:1112/1.; Subject Files; Records of Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty Research Institute; Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives at Central European University, Budapest.

HU OSA 300-40-2:23/3.; Subject Files in English; Records of Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty Research Institute; Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives at Central European University, Budapest.

HU OSA 300-40-3:9/64.; Subject Card Files; Records of Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty Research Institute; Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives at Central European University, Budapest.

HU OSA 300-40-4:20/22.; Information Items; Records of Radio Free Europe/Radio Liberty Research Institute; Vera and Donald Blinken Open Society Archives at Central European University, Budapest.

Secondary literature

Böcü, Gözde. "Home and Host Country Policy Interaction in the Making of Turkey's Diasporas" *Middle East Critique* 31, no. 4 (2022): 355-370.

Böcü, Gözde and Baser, Bahar. "Transnational Mobilization of Future Generations by Non-Democratic Home States: Turkey's Diaspora Youth Between Empowerment and Co-optation." *Ethnopolitics* (2022): 1-25.

Cude, Michael and Paul, Ellen. "Czechoslovakia." In *East Central European Migrations During the Cold War*, edited by Anna Mazurkiewicz, 101-135. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2019.
Gamlen, Alan J. "Diaspora Engagement Policies: What are they and what kinds of states use them?" *Working Paper* 32. Oxford: University of Oxford, 2006.

Gibbs, Graham R. *Analyzing Qualitative Data*. London: Sage Publications Ltd, 2007.

Holt, Robert. *Radio Free Europe*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1958.

Laguerre, Michel S. *Diasporic Citizenship: Haitian Americans in Transnational America*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 1998.

Levitt, Peggy and de la Dehesa, Rafael. "Transnational Migration and the Redefinition of the State: Variations and Explanations." *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 26, no. 4 (2003): 587-611.

Łukasiewicz, Sławomir. "The Polish Political System in Exile, 1945-1990." *Polish American Studies* 72, no. 2 (Autumn 2015): 13-31.

Pogonyi Szabolcs. "Transborder Kin-minority as Symbolic Resource in Hungary." *Journal on Ethnopolitics and Minority Issues in Europe* 14, no. 3 (2015): 73-98.

Ragazzi, Francesco. "A Comparative Analysis of Diaspora Policies." *Political Geography* 41 (2014): 74–89.

Shain, Yossi. "The Role of Diasporas in Conflict Perpetuation or Resolution." *SAIS Review* 12, no. 2 (2002):115-144.

Tsourapas, Gerasimos. "Theorizing State-Diaspora Relations in the Middle East: Authoritarian Emigration States in Comparative Perspective." *Mediterranean Politics* 25, no. 2 (2020): 135–159.